

Integrative Islamic Religious Instruction for Character Building: A Case Study at SD Integral Lukman Al-Hakim

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ABSTRACT

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Purpose: This study aimed to examine the implementation of integrative Islamic education (PAI) instruction at SD Integral Lukman Al-Hakim and its impact on students' character building. The primary focus of this research was to describe the mechanisms of integrating Islamic values with general subjects, identify the applied teaching methods, and analyze their contributions to students' cognitive, affective, and psychomotor development.

Methods: This study employed a qualitative approach with a case study design. Data was collected through semi-structured interviews, classroom observations, and document analysis, including lesson plans, teaching modules, and evaluation records. Data analysis followed the steps of data condensation, presentation via flowcharts and diagrams, and interpretation through meaning analysis, strengthened by triangulation techniques to ensure validity. The research site was strategically selected due to the school's commitment to implementing innovative integrative PAI learning through an interdisciplinary approach.

Results: The findings indicated that the integrative PAI instruction successfully synergized Islamic values with general subjects such as Indonesian Language, Mathematics, Natural Sciences (IPA), and Citizenship Education (PPKn). Using thematic integrative instruction, project-based learning, and problem-based learning proved effective in enhancing students' comprehension of Islamic concepts while fostering empathy, discipline, and social skills. Despite challenges such as time constraints and limited facilities, integrating digital technology and audiovisual media significantly created an interactive and contextual learning environment.

Conclusion: This study concluded that the integrative PAI instruction model effectively optimized character development in elementary education by holistically integrating academic and moral values. The findings provided practical implications for curriculum development and the enhancement of educators' competencies in addressing the challenges of 21st-century education.

KEYWORDS:

Integrative instruction; Islamic religious education; character building; case study; elementary education

1. INTRODUCTION

The evolution of modern education necessitates innovation in teaching methods that focus on academic achievement and character development (Abdulkarimova, 2023; Husnutdinov & Gilmanov, 2024; Turnsek, 2024; Syadzali et al., 2024). One such innovation is implementing integrative Islamic Religious Education (PAI) instruction, which combines Islamic values with other disciplines.

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This integration aims to create a synergy that unites spiritual, moral, and intellectual aspects, enabling students to develop holistically (Adiyono et al., 2024; Hastuty & Tobroni, 2024). Amid the dynamic changes in curricula and contemporary educational expectations, the integrative approach in Islamic Education emerges as a strategic alternative to overcome the limitations of conventional methods that tend to separate religious content from general subjects (Irmawati, 2024).

In many educational institutions, particularly at the elementary level, PAI instruction is still conducted traditionally, with a clear separation between religious studies and general subjects. This division potentially hinders the cohesion between spiritual values and academic knowledge, which ideally should support each other. Such conditions may result in a less optimal internalization of moral values,

impeding the holistic character formation of students. In response to these challenges, previous studies have suggested that integrating Islamic values with other disciplines can enhance educational quality and strengthen character development (Hidayat, 2024; Dahirin & Rusmin, 2024).

Similarly, a curriculum model combining Natural Sciences (IPA) with the Qur'an harmonizes educational objectives, content, and instructional time allocation. This model successfully created a holistic educational environment where students not only master scientific knowledge but also receive deep reinforcement of Islamic values. These findings align with the idea that an integrative approach bridges the gap between academic mastery and character formation, ultimately fostering well-rounded individual development (Hassan, 2016; Muamar et al., 2024).

Incorporating digital technology in the learning process further expands the dimensions of integrative PAI instruction. Digital media such as Google Classroom, PowerPoint, and other multimedia applications not only facilitate interactive content delivery but also serve as tools that integrate religious teachings with general subjects in a modern and contextually relevant manner. Technology allows educators to create innovative, engaging, and adaptive learning environments, enhancing instructional effectiveness and internalizing moral values among students (Amrullah et al., 2024; Herlina et al., 2024; Yahya et al., 2024).

Although various studies have explored the implementation of integrative instruction, most have focused on the context of Islamic secondary schools or higher education (Sahil et al., 2022; Arifin et al., 2023; Munawwaroh & Putri, 2024; Hastuty & Tobroni, 2024). However, this limitation presents an opportunity to fill the research gap at the elementary level, particularly in schools with unique characteristics, such as SD Integral Lukman Al-Hakim in Bojonegoro. Elementary education has distinct dynamics and challenges due to students' cognitive, affective, and social development. Thus, integrative PAI instruction in this context requires an in-depth study that accounts for young children's specific environment and learning processes.

Conceptually, integrative PAI instruction is founded on integrating Islamic values with modern scientific knowledge across several levels: philosophical, methodological, content-based, strategic, and evaluative. At the philosophical level, integration emphasizes a deep understanding of fundamental values that underlie relationships between humans, nature, and God, ensuring that moral instruction does not stand alone but interconnects with disciplines such as sociology, psychology, and philosophy (Musmuallim, 2013; Adawiyah, 2016). At the methodological level, educators must adopt empirical and deductive research approaches that connect Islamic theories with contemporary social phenomena (Afifah, 2024; Irmawati, 2024). Integration at the content and strategic levels involves curriculum adaptation and

implementing interdisciplinary teaching models, such as active learning and cross-disciplinary teaching teams, designed to facilitate dynamic and participatory teaching and learning processes. Finally, a comprehensive evaluation is necessary to measure the effectiveness of this integration in shaping students' character and social attitudes (Syafiqurrohman, 2020; Ibrahim & Andriyadi, 2022; Afifah, 2024; Irmawati, 2024; Tata et al., 2024).

The urgency of this study is further reinforced by the pressing need to adopt responsive teaching models that address contemporary educational challenges. Amid the widespread use of digital technology in education, integrating modern instructional media with Islamic values is highly relevant for creating an adaptive educational ecosystem (Gultom et al., 2025; Rishan et al., 2024; Zakiyyah et al., 2024). An interdisciplinary approach that harmonizes academic expectations with spiritual values enhances students' intellectual competence and character dimensions, such as honesty, responsibility, and social awareness (Rifai et al., 2023; Adiyono et al., 2024). Hence, this study aims to produce theoretical and practical findings for formulating more holistic and contextual Islamic teaching strategies.

The research conducted at SD Integral Lukman Al-Hakim in Bojonegoro occupies a strategic position as it explores the dynamics of integrative instruction implementation within elementary education. This case study offers insights into best practices, obstacles, and the potential for curriculum development responsive to social and technological transformations. The novelty of this research lies in its emphasis on merging academic aspects with Islamic values through an interdisciplinary approach, supported by the use of digital technology as an interactive and innovative medium. This approach is designed to comprehensively examine how integrating Islamic content with general subjects can positively impact students' attitudes, morality, and character development from an early age.

In this context, this study identifies several key focuses, including (1) describing the implementation mechanism of integrative PAI instruction in elementary school settings, (2) examining the role of digital technology in supporting interdisciplinary learning approaches, and (3) analyzing the impact of such integration on students' character development, encompassing affective, cognitive, and spiritual dimensions. A qualitative case study approach was employed to capture the local context in-depth, providing a comprehensive overview of the practices and effectiveness of the applied learning model. This methodology facilitated data collection through observations, interviews, and relevant document analysis, offering valuable insights into the actual dynamics in the field.

Furthermore, this study considers the role of evaluation as a crucial aspect in measuring the success of integrative instruction implementation. The evaluation was conducted to assess academic achievements and determine how students

internalized Islamic values through innovative teaching approaches. Using a holistic evaluative framework, this study aimed to provide strategic recommendations for educators and policymakers in designing more effective curricula and instructional models. Thus, the research findings are expected to address practical needs in developing educational models that harmoniously integrate academic and character dimensions, ultimately producing graduates who excel intellectually while maintaining strong moral and ethical foundations.

Integrating PAI and general subjects offers significant potential in shaping a new educational paradigm that aligns with contemporary social and technological dynamics. This study enriches educational literature by addressing existing research gaps in elementary education. The findings from the case study at SD Integral Lukman Al-Hakim Bojonegoro are expected to serve as a reference for developing more structured, innovative, and contextual integrative instruction approaches, significantly impacting character development and improving overall educational quality.

Through this study, more profound insights into the implementation of integrative PAI instruction are expected to guide educators in adopting innovative teaching strategies, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration, and optimizing the use of technology. As a result, students will experience learning that emphasizes academic aspects and strengthens essential Islamic values in their social lives. Ultimately, these findings are anticipated to become a strategic reference in the reform of elementary education curricula in Indonesia, ensuring that the resulting educational model can address global challenges and enhance the quality of human resources through character development rooted in religious and social ethics.

II. METHOD

This study employed a qualitative approach with a case study design. The qualitative approach was chosen to explore and understand the meanings emerging from implementing integrative PAI instruction in character development. Qualitative research emphasizes deep comprehension of social phenomena through naturally collected and non-manipulated data (Creswell, 2007; Creswell & Poth, 2016). As a research design, a case study allowed for an in-depth analysis of a specific case within its original context. This case study design was based on detailed evaluation principles (Creswell, 2007; Yin, 2018).

The study was conducted at SD Integral Luqman Al-Hakim Bojonegoro. This location was selected due to its strong commitment to implementing integrative PAI instruction, which combined a tauhid-based educational approach, the interaction between religious and general knowledge, and a solid dedication to character development. The school's supportive environment and structured teaching programs were strategic factors in selecting this research site.

For the case study, research participants were selected based on their roles and contributions to the learning process within the school. The participants included: (1) the principal, who oversaw educational policies and program directions; (2) the vice principals, responsible for curriculum and student affairs, providing in-depth information on curriculum implementation; (3) teachers, as direct executors of daily instruction processes, actively involved in applying the integrative PAI model; (4) parents, who offered perspectives on character changes in students post-learning implementation; and (5) students, the central subjects of this study, particularly in the observation of attitude transformations and character formation (Sugiyono, 2012).

Data was collected using three main techniques: a) Interviews: Semi-structured interviews were conducted with teachers, parents, and school administrators to obtain information regarding the learning process, teaching strategies, and evaluating Islamic values internalization. This interview technique allowed researchers to explore the informants' in-depth views and experiences (Creswell, 2015). b) Observations: Data were collected through direct observations of classroom learning activities and interactions between teachers and students. Observations were documented via field notes and, when possible, audio/visual recordings to capture the dynamics of the learning process. c) Documentation: Information was gathered from school documents such as teaching modules, lesson plans, syllabi, and character evaluation records. These data provided insights into instructional content, teaching strategies, and indicators of students' character development (Creswell, 2007; Creswell & Poth, 2016; Yin, 2018).

The validity of the data was ensured through triangulation techniques, which involved credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability tests. Data verification was conducted by comparing interview results, observations, and document analysis to ensure the consistency of findings in the field (Sugiyono, 2012). This confirmation process guaranteed that data interpretations aligned with actual realities.

Data analysis followed the procedures Miles et al. outlined, consisting of three stages: data condensation, data display, and conclusion drawing. The data condensation phase involved categorizing information based on key themes, while data display was structured using flowcharts, graphs, and tables to facilitate interpretation. In the final stage, researchers performed meaning analysis to confirm and validate the findings, leading to in-depth conclusions regarding the impact of integrative PAI instruction on students' character development (Miles et al., 2014).

III. RESULTS

Based on interviews with several PAI teachers and field observations, it was found that integrative PAI instruction at this school was implemented by incorporating Islamic teachings into various subjects, such as Indonesian Language,

Mathematics, Natural Sciences (IPA), Citizenship Education (PPKn), and Physical and Health Education (PJOK).

A. Components of Integrative PAI Instruction

One of the main aspects identified in this study was integrating PAI material with other subjects designed to develop students’ character. At SD Integral Lukman Al-Hakim, various PAI topics were combined with other subjects to strengthen students’ understanding of morals and character. For example, the topic “Morality toward Allah, the Prophet, and Oneself” was integrated with Citizenship Education (PPKn), Indonesian Language, and Cultural Arts. The values of faith and devotion to Allah were taught through love for the homeland and appreciation of diversity embedded in the PPKn curriculum.

Similarly, the topic “Morality toward Parents and Others” was linked with values contained in the Indonesian Language, PPKn, Social Studies (IPS), and Physical Education. In Indonesian Language classes, students were taught to write letters or essays expressing respect and love for parents and peers, aligning with Islamic teachings on honouring parents and fellow human beings.

Teachers at SD Integral Lukman Al-Hakim stated that this integration aimed to teach moral and social values embedded in Islam while connecting them with the subjects taught in class. Thus, students acquired knowledge about Islamic teachings and understood how to apply these values in their daily lives.

B. Integrative PAI Instruction Methods

Implementing various teaching methods was an integral part of the integrative PAI approach. Based on teacher interviews, several learning methods were applied at this school (Table 1).

Table 1. Integrative PAI Instruction Methods

No.	Methods	Summary Description
1	Thematic Integrative Instruction	Integrating Islamic Education (PAI) with other subjects under a single theme relevant to students’ daily lives, such as the “Clean Thursday” program.
2	Project-Based Learning	Students work in groups on projects that link PAI with other subjects, such as calculating zakat and preparing reports.
3	Problem-Based Learning	Through group discussions, students identify solutions to everyday issues, such as zakat or prayer, based on Islamic teachings.
4	Demonstration	Teachers directly demonstrate the application of Islamic teachings, such as performing ablution (wudu) or prayer,

while connecting them to other subjects.

5	Audiovisual	Utilizing media such as videos or images to explain PAI materials and relate them to other subjects.
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First, Thematic Integrative Instruction. This method integrated PAI materials with other subjects within a single theme relevant to students’ daily lives. For example, the “Clean Thursday” program, in which students participated in cleaning activities, taught social values and reinforced Islamic teachings on cleanliness. In this learning method, students also studied the impact of cleanliness on health and the environment, as explained in Natural Sciences (IPA).

Second, Project-Based Learning (PjBL). In this method, students worked in groups to complete projects integrating PAI topics with other subjects. For example, students were encouraged to calculate and distribute zakat, which required mathematical skills to compute zakat and Indonesian language skills to prepare reports on the activity. This method proved highly effective in developing students’ social skills and providing direct experience applying Islamic teachings in daily life.

Third, Problem-Based Learning (PBL). This method required students to identify real-life problems related to Islamic teachings, such as zakat or prayer, and find solutions based on Islamic principles. Students engaged in deep analysis of issues and sought answers through group discussions, which enhanced their analytical and problem-solving skills.

Fourth, Demonstration Method. Teachers used this method to provide direct examples of Islamic practices, such as performing ablution (wudu) or prayer. This learning approach was conducted within PAI classes and integrated into other subjects, such as the Indonesian Language, where students participated in writing prayers they had learned.

Lastly, the Audiovisual Method. Audiovisual media, such as videos of prophetic stories or illustrations, was employed to clarify lesson content and improve students’ comprehension. Through video-based learning, students learned about Islamic teachings and connected them to other subjects, such as Natural Sciences (IPA) and Citizenship Education (PPKn).

These integrative teaching strategies demonstrated that embedding Islamic values within general subjects enriched students’ understanding and facilitated the internalization of moral principles in various academic disciplines.

C. Impact of Integrative PAI Instruction on Character Development

Integrative PAI instruction at SD Integral Lukman Al-Hakim significantly impacted students’ character

development, particularly in cognitive, affective, and psychomotor skills (Table 2).

Table 2. Impact of Integrative PAI Instruction on Character Development

No.	Impact	Summary Description
1	Cognitive Skills	Students understood Islamic teachings about daily life and other subjects.
2	Affective Skills	Students developed positive attitudes such as empathy, patience, and responsibility.
3	Psychomotor Skills	Students honed practical teamwork, communication, and social engagement skills.

First, cognitive skills. Learning that integrated Islamic values with other subjects enabled students to comprehend religious teachings in a broader context. For example, zakat lessons not only taught the religious obligation but also incorporated mathematical concepts for calculating zakat and social skills for distributing it to those in need. Consequently, students acquired religious knowledge and practical skills beneficial for their daily lives.

Second, affective skills. Integrative PAI learning helped students cultivate empathy, patience, and a sense of responsibility. Through prophetic stories and examples from companions, students learned moral values taught in Islam, such as honesty, perseverance, and compassion toward others. These values were reflected in students' increased care for their peers, greater discipline in performing religious practices, and more active participation in social activities.

Lastly, psychomotor skills. Learning that involved physical activities, such as environmental cleanup projects and participation in social initiatives, helped students develop practical abilities. Additionally, their involvement in activities such as zakat collection, report writing, and prayer composition refined their writing, speaking, and teamwork skills.

D. Student Perceptions of Integrative PAI Instruction

Most students responded positively to integrative PAI learning. They felt that incorporating religious values into other subjects made the content more engaging and relevant to their daily lives. Students found it easier to understand Islamic teachings as they were able to connect the values to their experiences at school and home.

A fifth-grade student stated:

“Integrative PAI learning helped me better understand how to practice Islamic teachings in daily life, both at home and school. I realized that prayer, for example, is not just an obligation but also helps me feel more calm and disciplined.”

Additionally, students felt more valued as they had opportunities to share their personal stories and experiences within the learning material. The discussion- and project-based learning approaches encouraged students to be more engaged and actively participate in the learning process.

C. Challenges and Obstacles in Implementing Integrative PAI Learning

Although the implementation of integrative PAI instruction at SD Integral Lukman Al-Hakim yielded positive results, several challenges must be addressed. One of the main issues was limited instructional time, which often constrained the depth of project-based learning methods. Furthermore, insufficient facilities, such as projectors and teaching aids, posed obstacles to creating more interactive and engaging learning experiences.

Another challenge was the diversity of students' understanding of Islamic teachings. Some students had varying levels of comprehension, which affected the effectiveness of learning outcomes. Therefore, teachers needed to ensure that all students received equal opportunities to grasp the values taught in PAI learning.

IV. DISCUSSION

This study focuses on implementing integrative PAI instruction at SD Integral Lukman Al-Hakim, Bojonegoro, and its impact on students' character development. The findings illustrate how integrating Islamic values into various academic subjects shapes students' character across three primary dimensions: cognitive, affective, and psychomotor. This discussion connects these findings to existing literature, considering both supporting perspectives and potential challenges while emphasizing the relevance and contributions of this study within the context of elementary education.

Several previous studies highlight the importance of integrating religious values with academic subjects in character education. The studies on integrating Natural Sciences (IPA) with the Qur'an demonstrate that such an approach fosters holistic and in-depth education (Hassan, 2016; Muamar et al., 2024). The findings of this study align with that perspective, as the integration of PAI with general subjects such as Citizenship Education (PPKn), Indonesian Language, and Natural Sciences (IPA) significantly contributes to students' character development. This study reinforces the argument that learning models combining religious values with general knowledge can optimize both aspects without compromising. Consequently, the study provides empirical evidence that strengthens the existing literature on the significance of curriculum integration in elementary education.

Furthermore, this study supports the findings, which suggest that embedding moral values into science education enriches knowledge while fostering character development

(Hidayat, 2024; Dahirin & Rusmin, 2024). At SD Integral Lukman Al-Hakim, using thematic integrative methods, such as the “Clean Thursday” program, provides a concrete example of how Islamic teachings on cleanliness are taught alongside scientific concepts in IPA. The study’s findings align with previous research, highlighting that applying Islamic values in relevant academic contexts can shape students’ character.

Additionally, this study supports previous research, emphasizing technology’s role in integrative instruction (Amrullah et al., 2024; Herlina et al., 2024; Yahya et al., 2024). Although SD Integral Lukman Al-Hakim faces limitations in technological infrastructure, audiovisual media, such as prophetic story videos, enables more engaging and immersive teaching. By leveraging technology, teachers can connect moral values embedded in prophetic narratives with other subjects, such as IPA and PPKn. These findings underscore the study’s relevance to global educational trends, which increasingly incorporate technology to facilitate interactive and contextual learning experiences.

However, this study also identifies significant challenges in implementing integrative PAI learning, including time constraints and limited facilities. These challenges align with the findings, which highlight that project-based and problem-based teaching approaches require more instructional time than conventional methods (Krajcik & Shin, 2022; Zhao, 2024; Patrysha et al., 2024; Hidayati et al., 2024); thus, while theoretical perspectives emphasize the benefits of curriculum integration, real-world challenges such as infrastructural limitations and restricted time allocation present obstacles that need further attention, particularly in elementary education, where instructional dynamics differ from secondary schools or Islamic educational institutions (madrasahs).

This study underscores the importance of integrating character education into all aspects of learning. Lickona’s (2013) concept of character education suggests that character development should be at the core of all teaching practices and can be achieved through learning models that merge moral and academic values. The findings of this study strongly support Lickona’s theory, as the integrated learning approach implemented at SD Integral Lukman Al-Hakim emphasizes academic understanding and fosters students’ character by incorporating Islamic values into their daily lives.

The teaching methods used at this school, such as Project-Based Learning (PjBL) and Problem-Based Learning (PBL), align with the constructivist principles proposed by Piaget (1970) and Vygotsky (1978). These theories emphasize the importance of direct experience and social interaction in learning. At SD Integral Lukman Al-Hakim, students engage in group collaboration, problem-solving, and experiential learning through religion-based projects, such as zakat calculations and prayer practices. This approach enables

students to acquire knowledge while simultaneously developing social and character-building skills through collaboration, discussion, and direct application of the lessons they learn.

However, one aspect of this study presents a slight challenge to existing literature. While character education literature, such as that proposed by Lickona (2013), suggests that character is cultivated through holistic and integrated instruction, this study finds that students from diverse religious backgrounds may struggle to absorb values uniformly. This finding highlights the need for a more flexible approach to religious education, ensuring educators account for variations in students’ religious knowledge and comprehension. The study asserts that teaching religious values must be tailored to students’ understanding levels, ensuring no student is left behind in internalizing moral principles.

A key contribution of this study lies in its exploration of integrative PAI learning within elementary education. Existing literature focuses on secondary schools and madrasahs, with limited research on elementary-level implementation (Sahil et al., 2022; Arifin et al., 2023; Munawwaroh & Putri, 2024; Hastuty & Tobroni, 2024). This study fills that gap by examining how integrative learning can be applied in elementary schools and its impact on students’ character development. The findings offer empirical evidence demonstrating that embedding Islamic values into general subjects can be effectively implemented at the primary level, thereby fostering early character formation.

Moreover, this study proposes a concrete model for integrating PAI into a broader curriculum that combines character education theories with general disciplinary instruction. The suggested model, which incorporates PjBL and PBL methodologies, presents a new perspective in designing education that prioritizes not only academic achievement but also the holistic character development of students.

V. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that implementing integrative PAI instruction at SD Integral Lukman Al-Hakim, Bojonegoro, significantly impacted students’ character development. Through integrating Islamic values into various academic subjects such as Citizenship Education (PPKn), Natural Sciences (IPA), and Indonesian Language, students not only acquired religious knowledge but also developed strong moral attitudes, including responsibility, empathy, and social awareness. Learning methods such as thematic integrative learning, project-based learning (PjBL), and problem-based learning (PBL) proved effective in fostering students’ active participation and facilitating character development through direct experiences relevant to their daily lives.

The implications of these findings suggest that integrating PAI with other subjects can serve as an effective learning model for shaping students' character holistically. Therefore, other schools are encouraged to consider implementing integrative learning approaches to optimize character development, particularly at the elementary level. Additionally, to overcome challenges such as limited instructional time and inadequate facilities, schools should leverage educational technology to enrich the learning process and enhance teacher training to effectively adapt integrative teaching methods. Further research is needed to explore the long-term impact of integrative PAI learning on character development in broader educational contexts.

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VII. DISCLOSURE

The authors declare no financial or non-financial conflicts that could influence the interpretation or presentation of data in this work. All components of this research were conducted without any external support that could introduce bias, and no affiliations or relationships exist that could be perceived as conflicts of interest. This declaration ensures the integrity and objectivity of the study's findings per academic and research ethics standards

REFERENCES

1. Abdulkarimova, M. (2023). The Influence of New Methods of Modern Education on The Formation of a Person's Personality. *MMIT Proceedings*, 94–97. <https://doi.org/10.61587/mmit.uz.vi.19>
2. Adawiyah, R. (2016). Integrasi Sains dan Agama dalam Pembelajaran Kurikulum PAI (Perspektif Islam dan Barat serta Implementasinya). *Al-Banjari: Jurnal Ilmiah Ilmu-ilmu Keislaman*, 15(1), 99–124. <https://doi.org/10.18592/AL-BANJARI.V15I1.817>
3. Adiyono, A., Fitri, A. Z., & Al Matari, A. S. (2024). Uniting Science and Faith: A Re-STEAM Interdisciplinary Approach in Islamic Education Learning. *International Journal of Social Learning (IJSL)*, 4(3), 332–355. <https://doi.org/10.47134/ijsl.v4i3.281>
4. Afifah, S. N. (2024). Integrasi Teori Belajar dan Nilai Islam Dalam Pendidikan Modern: Konvergensi Untuk Pembelajaran Efektif. *Epistemic: Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan*, 3(2), 242–257. <https://doi.org/10.70287/epistemic.v3i2.8>
5. Amrullah, H. I., Amarta, A. N. F., Qurhahman, T., & Amali. (2024). Utilization of Media and Technology in Learning Islamic Religious Education. *Indonesian Journal of Contemporary Multidisciplinary Research*, 3(4), 583–588. <https://doi.org/10.55927/modern.v3i4.10010>
6. Arifin, S., Huda, M., & Mufida, N. (2023). Developing Akhlak Karimah Values through Integrative Learning Model in Madrasah. *JPI (Jurnal Pendidikan Islam)*, 9(1), 41–54. <https://doi.org/10.15575/jpi.v0i0.24443>
7. Creswell, J. W. (2007). *Qualitative Inquiry and Research Design: Choosing Among Five Traditions* (2nd ed.). SAGE Publications.
8. Creswell, J. W., & Poth, C. N. (2016). *Qualitative Inquiry & Research Design. In Qualitative Inquiry & Research Design* (4th ed.). SAGE Publication.
9. Dahirin, & Rusmin. (2024). Integrasi Nilai-Nilai Keislaman Pada Peserta Didik Melalui Pembelajaran Pendidikan Agama Islam. *Dirasah: Jurnal Studi Ilmu Dan Manajemen Pendidikan Islam*, 7(2), 762-771. <https://doi.org/10.58401/dirasah.v7i2.1325>
10. Gultom, Y., Candra, D., Dasopang, M. D., Sihombing, I., & Ali, M. K. (2025). Pendidikan Islam di Era Digital. *Indo-MathEdu Intellectuals Journal*, 6(1), 455–464. <https://doi.org/10.54373/imeij.v6i1.2567>
11. Hassan, N.J. (2016). Integrating the Qur'anic Worldview with the Natural Sciences: Answering the Call for Islamic Secondary Schools. In: Kamali, M., Bakar, O., Batchelor, DF., Hashim, R. (eds) *Islamic Perspectives on Science and Technology*. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-287-778-9_21
12. Hastuty, A., & Tobroni. (2024). Tinjauan Sistematis Literatur Implementasi PAI Multidisipliner pada Madrasah. *Dialektika: Jurnal Pendidikan Agama Islam*, 3(2), 12-20. <https://doi.org/10.35905/dialektika.v3i2.11553>
13. Herlina, H., Astuti, M., Triyunita, H., Rahmawati, T. D., & Yana, N. (2024). Pemanfaatan Media Digital dalam Menarik Minat Siswa di SD/MI Terhadap Pembelajaran PAI. *Indo-MathEdu Intellectuals Journal*, 5(6), 8265–8277. <https://doi.org/10.54373/imeij.v5i6.2431>
14. Hidayat, I. K. (2024). Integrating Islamic Education Values: The Key to Character Education of the Young

- Generation Al-Hikam Perspective. *EduReligia: Jurnal Pendidikan Agama Islam*, 8(1), 90–101. <https://doi.org/10.33650/edureligia.v8i1.8596>
15. Hidayati, A. U., Maulidin, S., & Kholifah, S. (2024). Implementasi Problem-Based Learning (PBL) pada Proses Pembelajaran PAI: Studi Di SMK Pelita Bangun Rejo. *Action: Jurnal Inovasi Penelitian Tindakan Kelas Dan Sekolah*, 4(2), 53-62. <https://doi.org/10.51878/action.v4i2.4144>
 16. Husnutdinov, A. N., & Gilmanov, M. M. (2024). Modern teaching methods in the context of innovations and quality education. *Ekonomika i Upravljenje: Problemy, Resheniâ*, 7/5(148), 65–73. <https://doi.org/10.36871/ek.up.p.r.2024.07.05.008>
 17. Ibrahim, A., & Andriyadi, F. (2022). Pendidikan Agama Islam Terintegrasi sebagai Pembentukan Karakter Mahasiswa. *Al-Ijtima'i: International Journal of Government and Social Science*, 7(2), 167–176. <https://doi.org/10.22373/jai.v7i2.1737>
 18. Irmawati, I. (2024). Integrasi Nilai-Nilai Islam dalam Kurikulum PAI. *Al-Mikraj: Jurnal Studi Islam dan Humaniora*, 4(2), 1743-1757. <https://doi.org/10.37680/almikraj.v4i02.5421>
 19. Krajcik, J. S., & Shin, N. (2022). Project-Based Learning. In R. K. Sawyer (Ed.), *The Cambridge Handbook of the Learning Sciences* (pp. 72–92). chapter, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
 20. Lickona, T. (2013). *Educating for character, Mendidik untuk Membentuk Karakter: Bagaimana Sekolah Dapat Mengajarkan Sikap Hormat dan Tanggungjawab* (3rd ed.). Bumi Aksara.
 21. Miles, M. B., Huberman, A. M., & Saldana, J. (2014). *Qualitative Data Analysis: A Methods Sourcebook* (3rd ed.). SAGE Publication.
 22. Muamar, M., Kartimi, K., & Rahtikawati, Y. (2024). Keterkaitan Al-Qur'an dan Ilmu Alam: Perspektif dalam Pembelajaran Pendidikan Agama di Sekolah. *Journal on Education*, 7(1), 8429–8435. <https://doi.org/10.31004/joe.v7i1.7641>
 23. Munawwaroh, I., & Putri, D. F. (2024). Enhancing Critical Thinking Through the Integration of Self-Directed Learning in Sustainable Education in Madrasah. *Afkarina: Jurnal Pendidikan Agama Islam*, 9(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.33650/afkarina.v9i1.9352>
 24. Musmuallim, M. (2013). Paradigma Pembelajaran Pendidikan Agama Islam Berwawasan Integratif. *Insania*, 18(2), 187-198. Retrieved from <https://ejournal.uinsaizu.ac.id/index.php/insania/article/download/1453/1055/2759>
 25. Patrysha, C., Azizah, N., & Gusmaneli, G. (2024). Meningkatkan Partisipasi Siswa Melalui Metode Project Based Learning dalam Pendidikan Agama Islam. *JISPENDIORA: Jurnal Ilmu Sosial, Pendidikan dan Humaniora*, 3(2), 01–12. <https://doi.org/10.56910/jispendorora.v3i2.1399>
 26. Piaget, J. (1970). *Genetic Epistemology*. The Norton Library.
 27. Rifai, A., Manshur, U., & Sayuri, S. (2023). Synergizing Science and Spirituality: Crafting an Integrated Curriculum to Elevate Spiritual Intelligence in Madrasah Education. *IJESS: Indonesian Journal of Education and Social Studies*, 2(1), 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.33650/ijess.v2i1.7111>
 28. Rishan, M., Batubara, J., & Deliani, N. (2024). Integrasi Teori Belajar Sosial dalam Pembelajaran Pendidikan Agama Islam di Era Digital. *Tsaqofah*, 4(6), 4318-4332. <https://doi.org/10.58578/tsaqofah.v4i6.4225>
 29. Sahil, J., Hasan, S. H., Ahmad, H., Majid, I., & Haerullah, A. (2022). Gagasan Penyusunan Rencana Pelaksanaan Pembelajaran Integratif Ilmu Umum dan Ilmu Agama di Madrasah. *Jurnal Bioedukasi*, 5(1), 25. <https://doi.org/10.33387/bioedu.v5i1.4384>
 30. Sugiyono. (2012). *Metode Penelitian kuantitatif, kualitatif dan R & D*. Alfabeta.
 31. Syadzali, A., Asrori, M., & Kawakip, A. (2024). Reimagining Character Education: Innovations in Cultivating Values Amidst the Advancements of Civilization. *Fikruna: Jurnal Ilmiah Kependidikan dan Kemasyarakatan*, 7(1), 185-222. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.56489/fik.v7i1.278>
 32. Syafiqurrohman, M. (2020). Implementasi Pendidikan Akhlak Integratif-Inklusif. *Qalamuna: Jurnal Pendidikan, Sosial, dan Agama*, 12(01), 37–48. <https://doi.org/10.37680/qalamuna.v12i01.240>
 33. Tata, S., Suhara, D., & Nur, W. (2024). Integrasi Pendidikan Agama Islam dengan Bimbingan Konseling dan Dampaknya Terhadap Akhlak Peserta Didik. *Ta'dib: Jurnal Pendidikan Agama Islam*, 2(1), 116–126. <https://doi.org/10.69768/jt.v2i1.52>
 34. Turnsek, M. S. (2024). Modern Students Demand Modern-Innovative Teaching. *Journal of Media & Management*, 6(4), 1–4. [https://doi.org/10.47363/jmm/2024\(6\)175](https://doi.org/10.47363/jmm/2024(6)175)
 35. Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in Society: The Development of Higher Psychological Processes*. Harvard University Press.
 36. Yahya, M. S., Fian, K., Afandi, R., & Masruri, M. (2024). The Effectiveness of IT-Based Audiovisual Media in Enhancing Islamic Religious Education Learning Outcomes: A Meta-Analysis. *Tadris: Jurnal Keguruan dan Ilmu Tarbiyah*, 9(2), 499-514. <https://doi.org/10.24042/tadris.v9i2.23624>
 37. Yin, R. K. (2018). *Case Study Research and Applications: Design and methods* (6th ed.). SAGE Publication.

38. Zakiyyah, I., Suparto, S., & Maswani, M. (2024). Learning Management of Islamic Religious Education Based on Digital Technology. *12th International Conference on Cyber and IT Service Management (CITSM), Batam, Indonesia*, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1109/citsm64103.2024.10775708>
39. Zhao, K. (2024). Project -based Learning and Students' Performance. *Frontiers in Business, Economics and Management*, 16(1), 401-405. <https://doi.org/10.54097/3cpp0337>